

Learning After Learning: Positive Backward Transfer in Continual Learning

Supplementary Material

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1 Experimental Setup

1.1 List of Hyperparameters

For the baselines and our approach, we detail the hyper-parameters in Table 1, n_s in GPM, TRPG and CUBER denotes the number of random training examples sampled from the replay buffer to construct the representation matrix. c in WSN, and LEAF denotes the percentage of weights stored per mask based on the highest weight scores s . For example, if c is set to 0.1, only 10% of the capacity at each layer would be stored for each mask. mem in A-GEM is the maximum amount of past task instances stored in the replay buffer. k in LEAF is set using grid search on the validation set. The value varies as the distance’s magnitude scale depends on the dataset. For A-GEM, GPM, and TRPG, the plain stochastic gradient descent optimiser (SGD) is used, while SupSup, WSN, and LEAF use the Adam optimiser [2]. The dataset characteristics can be seen in Table 3.

1.2 Performance Metrics

Following Lin et al. [5], we use accuracy (ACC) to evaluate performance, it is the average test classification accuracy of all tasks. Formally, ACC is defined as:

$$ACC = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T R_{T,i} \quad (1)$$

Here, T is the total number of sequential tasks and $R_{T,i}$ is the accuracy of the model on i^{th} task after learning the T^{th} task sequentially [6].

1.3 Datasets Characteristics

The overview of our datasets can be seen in Table 2, with the number of classes and instances per task seen in Table 3. The 5-Dataset is excluded from the table due to the variability in the number of classes and instances in each of the five datasets.

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Table 1. Hyperparameter setup for the baselines and LEAF (ours).

Methods	Hyperparameters
A-GEM	lr : 0.05 (cifar, cifar-sc), 0.1 (miniImg, tinyImg, 5D) mem: 2000 (cifar, cifar-sc), 500 (miniImg, tinyImg), 3000 (5D) optim : sgd
GPM	lr : 0.01 (cifar, cifar-sc), 0.1 (miniImg, tinyImg, 5D) n_s : 100 (miniImg, tinyImg, 5D), 125 (cifar, cifar-sc) optim : sgd
TRPG	lr : 0.01 (cifar, cifar-sc), 0.1 (miniImg, tinyImg, 5D) n_s : 100 (miniImg, tinyImg, 5D), 125 (cifar, cifar-sc) optim : sgd
SupSup	lr : 0.1 (cifar, cifar-sc), 0.001 (miniImg, tinyImg, 5D) optim : adam
WSN	lr : 0.1 (cifar, cifar-sc), 0.001 (miniImg, tinyImg, 5D) optim : adam c : 0.3 (cifar, cifar-sc, 5D), 0.1 (miniImg, tinyImg)
LEAF	lr : 0.1 (cifar, cifar-sc), 0.001 (miniImg, tinyImg, 5D) c : 0.3 (cifar, cifar-sc, 5D), 0.1 (miniImg, tinyImg) k : 3 (miniImg), 6 (cifar, 5D), 12 (cifar-sc), 16 (tinyImg) mem: 5000 (cifar), 2500 (cifar-sc, tinyImg), 2375 (miniImg) optim : adam

Hyperparameters for: CIFAR100 (cifar), CIFAR100-SC (cifar-sc), MiniImageNet (miniImg), TinyImageNet (tinyImg), and 5 Datasets (5D)

Table 2. Dataset Characteristics

	Tasks	Classes	Number of instances
CIFAR100	10	100	60000
CIFAR100-SC	20	100	60000
TinyImageNet	40	200	120000
MiniImageNet	20	100	60000

2 LEAF Running Example

Figure 1 illustrates LEAF’s model training process when a new task t_3 is introduced, following the learning of t_1 and t_2 . The chosen task had been set to t_1 , and the instances of t_1 were inserted into the replay buffer \mathcal{M} for future use when updating the chosen task mask m_{t_c} . As shown in Step (a), to define a subnetwork for task t_3 , we find the task mask illustrated in Step (b). This process shows the learning process during each epoch by showing how the model weights

Table 3. Dataset Characteristics Per Task

	Classes #	Train #	Val #	Test #
CIFAR100	10	4750	250	1000
CIFAR100-SC	5	2375	125	500
TinyImageNet	5	2375	125	500
MiniImageNet	5	2375	125	500

and score are updated to find the highest accuracy task mask. In the weight optimization phase, weights highlighted in blue are frozen, as they were previously selected by task masks of t_1 and t_2 . However, the scores s are still updated to allow us to select weights from previous tasks, enabling forward knowledge transfer. Upon identifying the ideal subnetwork, the top 10% of weights, based on their scores s , are chosen to form the task mask m_3 , which signifies the subnetwork the task t_3 will use during inference. These weights included in the subnetwork will be frozen for future iterations.

Once a task mask is created, Step (c) evaluates whether an update is needed for the chosen task t_c . This step determines if there is sufficient knowledge to improve the chosen task by measuring the distance between the gradients. The instances from the replay buffer of the chosen task t_1 are used to compute the gradient change of each layer. Two sets of gradients are generated: one by passing data through the chosen task mask M_1 to obtain g_1 , and another through the accumulated masks $M_2 \cup M_3$ to produce G . The value of g_1 is $\langle 0.2, \dots, 0.5 \rangle$ and the value of G is $\langle 0.7, \dots, 0.2 \rangle$, these are then used to calculate the Wasserstein distance to measure how influential a gradient update will be on other tasks. The distance measure helps us estimate the influence of updating the modified accumulated binary mask with instances from the chosen task. The output distance measure of 1.08 is then fed into the CUSUM change detector, which measures if an update is required.

Upon detecting a significant change, as shown in Step (d), the chosen task mask m_{t_c} is updated using data from the replay buffer. The mask is temporarily unfrozen, enabling updates to the weights selected by the chosen task to be updated. Consequently, the task mask is updated on the new model weights after learning tasks t_2 and t_3 , which differs from its original mask selection. This method facilitates the integration of newly acquired knowledge into the revised task mask for the chosen task.

3 More Experimental Results

3.1 Performance on a dataset with overlapping data

Backward transfer is quantified as the average accuracy improvement of the chosen task after learning all subsequent tasks. This indicates that learning new tasks can enhance understanding of similar, previously learned tasks. To better understand this, we consider a unique setup proposed by [4]. Specifically, in a setup where CIFAR100 has overlapping classes between tasks, we split the first 50 classes in CIFAR100 into 7 tasks (OL-CIFAR100): Tasks 0-6 contain classes 0-9, 5-14, 10-19, 20-29, 25-34, 30-39, 40-49, respectively. The ACC and BWT_{t_c} of LEAF is compared with the backward transfer methods: GPM, TRGP, and CUBER, as shown in Table 4. LEAF outperforms GPM, TRGP, and CUBER in both ACC and BWT_{t_c} . In particular, LEAF has a BWT_{t_c} of 0.28% over CUBER and 1.03% over TRGP.

Figure 1. Example model learning process with LEAF

Table 4. ACC and standard deviation values for OL-CIFAR100 dataset

	ACC (%)	BWT_{t_c} (%)
GPM	71.3 ± 0.66	-1.87 ± 1.67
TRGP	74.7 ± 0.74	0.15 ± 0.49
CUBER	75.18 ± 0.35	0.90 ± 0.37
LEAF (ours)	77.80 ± 0.15	1.18 ± 0.58

3.2 LEAF potential accuracy in full task utilization

This experiment aims to assess the full potential of LEAF in a relaxed setting, termed LEAF+All, where all past data can be accessed individually, and every task is sequentially treated as a chosen task. This setup allows us to assess the potential of LEAF when multiple tasks can benefit from the BWT. The results are shown in Table 5, and LEAF+All improves BWT across various datasets. For instance, in the CIFAR100, CIFAR100-SC, and MiniImageNet, LEAF+All achieves a BWT of 0.38%, 0.73%, and 3.46%, respectively. The

Table 5. The *BWT* and standard deviation values over 5 seeds. LEAF+All is the case where all tasks are chosen

	CIFAR100	CIFAR100-SC	TinyImageNet	5 Dataset	MiniImageNet
A-GEM (ICLR 19)	-0.21 ± 0.14	-0.31 ± 0.29	-2.31 ± 0.85	-0.91 ± 0.55	-1.01 ± 0.24
GPM (ICLR 21)	-0.15 ± 0.10	-0.70 ± 0.24	-1.61 ± 0.70	-1.24 ± 0.28	-1.44 ± 0.93
TRGP (ICLR 22)	-0.07 ± 0.05	-1.10 ± 0.30	-0.11 ± 0.02	-0.04 ± 0.06	-0.37 ± 0.13
CUBER (Neurips 22)	0.14 ± 0.06	0.08 ± 0.08	-0.35 ± 0.10	-0.03 ± 0.03	0.16 ± 0.16
LEAF+All (ours)	0.38 ± 0.19	0.73 ± 0.37	1.18 ± 0.67	-0.16 ± 0.17	3.46 ± 0.88

BWT improvements by LEAF+All notably exceed the performance of other CL methods like GPM, TRGP, A-GEM, and CUBER, indicating a substantial improvement in LEAF’s ability to use BWT when not limited by memory constraints. The 3.46% BWT increase on MiniImageNet notably shows LEAF+All’s effectiveness in using knowledge from all tasks. These results show that LEAF may be suitable for scenarios with limited run-time but sufficient storage for past data.

4 Discussion

4.1 Single Task Scenario

The single-task scenario in our study highlights the growing need in CL, particularly in domains like robotics [8] and automated driving systems [3]. Specific tasks are critical in real-world applications and cannot be compromised despite acquiring new tasks. For instance, a health monitoring device’s capability to detect diabetes [7], and even advanced driver assistance systems [3] must not only remain dependable but also improve over time. Our approach challenges the traditional CL paradigm by emphasizing maintaining and improving a critical task. This alignment with practical needs in robotics and similar fields represents a significant move towards more targeted and applicable CL strategies.

4.2 Backward Transfer and Catastrophic Forgetting

Our work on backward transfer focuses on task mask methods, separating learning tasks into distinct subnetworks. Although effective in mitigating CF by preventing any change to previously learned tasks, it limits the ability for previous tasks to evolve as the network acquires new knowledge. LEAF mitigates this limitation by improving the accuracy of previous tasks, bridging a critical gap in CL. The ability for tasks to transfer knowledge to older tasks is particularly vital in real-world applications, where the continual improvement of older tasks are as crucial as learning new ones.

4.3 Memory Storage and Run-time Memory

In CL, BWT methods store task representations through data instances or gradients [4, 1]. Our experiments show a trade-off between improving the accuracy of a learned task and the need to store past data. We identify two types of memory. Persistent memory stores the gradients and data, and run-time memory stores the additional information derived from persistent memory. For example, Lin et al. [4] store small gradient vectors. However, large complex matrices are then calculated to achieve BWT, leading to a significant increase in run-time memory, particularly in larger models. In contrast, LEAF requires lower run-time memory as only the data instances are required for backward transfer. LEAF maintains a steady level of persistent storage, only loading the past data into run-time memory during the update assessment or a chosen task mask update. Thus, LEAF

may be suitable in scenarios where run-time memory is limited but sufficient persistent storage is available.

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